

Supplementary appendix S4: Funnel plot and Egger's test graph of outcomes

Figure 1. Funnel plot of acupuncture plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the HAMD-17 score at different types of acupuncture (MA/EA)

Figure 2. Funnel plot of acupuncture plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the SDS score at different types of acupuncture (MA/EA)

Figure 3. Funnel plot of EA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the treatment response of HAMD-17

Figure 4. Funnel plot of MA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the number of participants who reported adverse drug reactions

Figure 5. Egger's test graph of acupuncture plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the HAMD-17 score at different types of acupuncture (MA/EA)

Figure 6. Egger's test graph of acupuncture plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the SDS score at different types of acupuncture (MA/EA)

Figure 7. Egger's test graph of EA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the treatment response of HAMD-17

Figure 8. Egger's test graph of MA plus antidepressants versus antidepressants alone on the number of participants who reported adverse drug reactions